

Vacuums of the sea: ecological function of large coral reef benthic scavengers in suppressing crown-of-thorns starfish (COTS) outbreaks

Mohsen Kayal^{1,2}, Hunter S. Lenihan³

¹ENTROPIE, IRD, Université de la Réunion, CNRS, IFREMER, Université de la

Nouvelle-Calédonie, Noumea, New Caledonia (mohsen.kayal@ird.fr)

²Laboratoire d'Excellence CORAIL, Paris, France

³Bren School of Environmental Science and Management, University of California, Santa Barbara, USA (hlenihan@ucsb.edu)

Abstract

Despite their drastic impacts on coral reefs, outbreaks of the coral-feeding seastar crown-of-thorns starfish (COTS), *Acanthaster*, have remained a scientific enigma. Significant efforts in coral reef conservation science have been dedicated to identifying natural predators able to exert demographic control on the seastar and prevent population outbreaks. These efforts are motivated by empirical evidence showing that reefs within protected areas are less prone to COTS outbreaks than reefs open to fishing where potential COTS predators have been reduced or removed functionally from food webs. Research findings point towards COTS' early life-stages as a major demographic bottleneck for COTS populations, with various reef fish and benthic organisms identified as preying upon the seastar. Yet, no species or species groups have been clearly identified as exerting enough top-down control to influence COTS population increases or prevent outbreaks. We report the feeding behavior of the large-bodied benthic scavenger eagle ray (family Myliobatidae) in New Caledonia feeding in coral rubble

fields, critical habitats where juvenile COTS find refuge and food and accumulate to produce population outbreaks. We argue that with their effective substrate-sucking feeding behavior, similar to vacuums of the sea, eagle rays may be a hitherto unidentified predator able to exert significant control on COTS populations. Eagle rays and other large benthic scavengers were previously neglected in the search for major COTS predators. The relatively little existing data show that eagle ray populations in New Caledonia's lagoon are more abundant inside than outside marine protected areas, which concords with the hypothesis that they could be responsible for the mitigation of COTS outbreaks as reported within reserves. We advocate for further investigations on the role of eagle rays and other large benthic scavengers in controlling COTS outbreaks, and underscore the importance of preserving the unique ecological function of sea vacuums for coral reef conservation.

Keywords

Coral reef, Crown-of-thorns starfish, *Acanthaster*, Seastar, Predator outbreak, Eagle ray.

Unresolved mystery around COTS outbreaks

Outbreaks of crown-of-thorns starfish (COTS, *Acanthaster* spp.) cause mass coral mortality and are a clear threat to coral reef conservation in an era of global coral decline (Kayal et al. 2012, Pratchett et al. 2017, Condie et al. 2021). There has been a long running debate about the mechanisms that control COTS outbreaks, which in part remain a scientific enigma. Two non-mutually exclusive, predominant hypotheses about the mechanisms exerting demographic bottlenecks for COTS populations have been proposed, both of which are supported by a relatively large body of empirical evidence (Pratchett et al. 2014). The bottom-up “nutrient enrichment hypothesis” emphasizes the importance of nutrient availability for phytoplankton

blooms upon which COTS larvae feed and rely upon during their transition from pelagic to benthic stages: with eutrophication of reef environments, COTS populations increase due to increased recruitment and early life stage survivorship (Fabricius et al. 2010, Wooldridge & Brodie 2015, Matthews et al. 2020). The top-down “predation release hypothesis” emphasizes the role of species feeding upon the seastar in regulating their populations, a mechanism altered when reef fisheries reduce local abundances of COTS predators (Cowan et al. 2017). Quantitative evidence indicates that COTS outbreaks are more frequent and intense outside of marine protected areas than in reef areas protected from fishing, thereby supporting the predation release hypothesis (Dulvy et al. 2004, Sweatman 2008, McCook et al. 2010, Mellin et al. 2016, Vanhatalo et al. 2017, Westcott et al. 2020, Kroon et al. 2021). Nevertheless, the evidence to support the predation release hypothesis is correlative and circumstantial, and there is need for improved knowledge on the mechanisms through which protection from fishing benefits control of COTS populations. Specifically, identifying species exerting significant control on COTS populations can help define targeted management actions that support coral reef resilience.

Our hypothesis

We propose the hypothesis that foraging by eagle rays (family *Myliobatidae*), large-bodied bottom scavengers feeding in coral reef rubble fields, can exert significant top-down control of COTS juvenile life-stages, thereby playing a key role in regulating COTS outbreaks. Our hypothesis is based on observations of active foraging of the reef substrate in New Caledonia by an eagle ray, moving coral rubble around and sucking up potential prey hidden in the substrate and around live corals (Fig. 1). Because coral rubble fields constitute predominant habitats for COTS juvenile stages (Zann et al. 1987, Wilmes et al. 2020b), we argue that such feeding behavior, acting as a vacuum of the sea substrate, may constitute a key ecological

function regulating marine benthic invertebrate populations, including COTS whose outbreaks can devastate corals at large spatial scales.

Figure 1 Photograph of an eagle ray (family Myliobatidae) foraging the shallow reef substrate in New Caledonia. The individual was observed moving coral rubbles and sucking up potential prey from the reef substrate, a suction feeding behavior comparable to a vacuum of the sea. We believe that this ecological function may be critical for regulating invertebrate populations hiding in the substrate, such as juveniles of the coral predator crown-of-thorns starfish. See video at Kayal (2024).

Support for our hypothesis

Recent research efforts have focused on identifying COTS predators in an endeavor to improve coral reef management through the regulation of COTS outbreaks exerted by their natural predators. More than 100 species of reef fish and invertebrates have been identified as preying upon the seastar at different life stages and health conditions (Cowan et al. 2017). However, predation on early COTS life stages remains largely under-characterized, while seastar survival in the juvenile stage — that is when the small, cryptic, and coralline feeding seastars are hiding within coral rubble habitats — is considered a major demographic bottleneck for COTS populations (Wilmes et al. 2018, 2020b). In an extensive review of the scientific literature, Cowan et al. (2017) concluded that predation on newly settled starfish is predominantly exerted by benthic invertebrates associated with coral rubble fields, a hypothesis currently under intensive investigation (Desbiens et al. 2023). However, research on putative predators of juvenile COTS have fundamentally dismissed the importance of large generalist reef predators that are able to effectively forage through coral rubble over expansive reef areas. Like other ray species, eagle rays are intensive bottom-feeders that effectively “vacuum” up invertebrate prey hidden in marine benthic substrate (Thrush et al. 1991, Hines et al. 1997, Ajemian et al. 2018, Fig. 1). A large body of research conducted in the 1980's solidified how foraging by bat rays in temperate latitude regions (Hulberg and Oliver 1980, Van Blaricom 1982), and sting rays in tropical latitudes (Thistle 1981), substantially influence soft-sediment invertebrate assemblages, either directly through predation or indirectly through physical disturbance (see Lenihan and Micheli 2001 for a review). Our observation of an eagle ray foraging in coral rubble suggests that they may be a key predator able to control COTS juvenile abundance and reduce outbreaks. Indeed, coral rubble provides important recruitment substrate, refuge, and coralline-algae food for juvenile

COTS (Zann et al. 1987, Wilmes et al. 2018, 2020a) and is where seastar density can build up over years into outbreaks (Deaker et al. 2020).

Juvenile COTS buried in coral rubble may not have many large predators (Cowan et al. 2017). Species acting as sea vacuums in rubble fields, like eagle ray, probably play a unique role in controlling COTS density build-ups and the frequency and intensity of outbreaks, which typically originate in habitats dominated by coral rubble (Zann et al. 1987, Johnson et al. 1991, Kayal et al. 2012, Wilmes et al. 2020b). Relatively healthy eagle ray populations may explain the relatively constrained COTS outbreaks observed in New Caledonia's lagoon, as compared with the neighboring regions Australia and Vanuatu where higher frequency and intensity of outbreaks are reported (Adjeroud et al. 2018). Although limitations in data currently prevent quantitatively testing this hypothesis, recent investigation in New Caledonia indicates eagle ray populations were three times more abundant inside than outside of marine reserves (Heudier et al. 2023), corroborating the hypothesis that they could be responsible for the mitigation of COTS outbreaks in protected areas as reported in different regions (Dulvy et al. 2004, Sweatman 2008, McCook et al. 2010, Mellin et al. 2016, Westcott et al. 2020, Kroon et al. 2021).

Conclusions and prospective research

Megafauna often play important roles in marine ecosystems, although their ecological functions are not always known or fully recognized, and their populations are often highly endangered by human activities (McCauley et al. 2015, Pimiento et al. 2020). Our observations shed light on the potentially unique ecological function of eagle rays for safeguarding coral reefs from COTS outbreaks. While we currently do not possess the

necessary information to test this hypothesis, future investigations may include eagle ray behavior and diet analyses to confirm or reject predation on juvenile COTS (Ajemian et al. 2012, Leray et al. 2013), and joint analysis of eagle ray and COTS populations to establish predator-prey regulation and a potential mitigation of outbreaks (Kayal et al. 2012). While diver operated COTS control efforts are costly but often considered as the best approach to reduce the impacts of their outbreaks (Westcott et al. 2020, Condie et al. 2021, Castro-Sanguino et al. 2023), coral reef resilience may significantly benefit from an increased protection of eagle ray populations and their important ecological function as vacuums of the reef.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by funding from the French Laboratory of Excellence CORAIL and the French Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

References

- Adjeroud, M., Kayal, M., Peignon, C., Juncker, M., Mills, S.C., Beldade, R. et al. 2018. Ephemeral and localized outbreaks of the coral predator *Acanthaster cf. solaris* in the southwestern lagoon of New Caledonia. *Zoological Studies* 57: 4.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.6620/ZS.2018.57-04>
- Ajemian, M.J., Powers, S.P. and T.J.T. Murdoch. 2012. Estimating the potential impacts of large mesopredators on benthic resources: integrative assessment of spotted eagle ray foraging ecology in Bermuda. *PLOS ONE* 7(7): e40227.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0040227>

- Castro-Sanguino, C., Bozec, Y.M., Condie, S.A., Fletcher, C.S., Hock, K., Roelfsema, C., et al. 2023. Control efforts of crown-of-thorns starfish outbreaks to limit future coral decline across the Great Barrier Reef. *Ecosphere* 14(6): e4580. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.4580>
- Condie, S.A., Anthony, K.R., Babcock, R.C., Baird, M.E., Beeden, R., Fletcher, C.S., et al. 2021. Large-scale interventions may delay decline of the Great Barrier Reef. *Royal Society Open Science* 8(4): 201296. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.201296>
- Cowan, Z.L., Pratchett, M., Messmer, V. and S. Ling. 2017. Known predators of crown-of-thorns starfish (*Acanthaster* spp.) and their role in mitigating, if not preventing, population outbreaks. *Diversity* 9(1): 7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d9010007>
- Deaker, D.J., Agüera, A., Lin, H.A., Lawson, C., Budden, C., Dworjanyn, S.A., et al. 2020. The hidden army: corallivorous crown-of-thorns seastars can spend years as herbivorous juveniles. *Biology Letters* 16(4): 20190849. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2019.0849>
- Desbiens, A.A., Mumby, P.J., Dworjanyn, S., Plagányi, É.E., Uthicke, S. and K. Wolfe. 2023. Novel rubble-dwelling predators of herbivorous juvenile crown-of-thorns starfish (*Acanthaster* sp.). *Coral Reefs* 42(2): 579-591. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-023-02364-w>
- Dulvy, N.K., Freckleton, R.P. and N.V. Polunin. 2004. Coral reef cascades and the indirect effects of predator removal by exploitation. *Ecology Letters* 7(5): 410-416. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2004.00593.x>
- Fabricius, K.E., Okaji, K. and G. De'ath. 2010. Three lines of evidence to link outbreaks of the crown-of-thorns seastar *Acanthaster planci* to the release of larval food limitation. *Coral Reefs* 29, 593–605. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-010-0628-z>

- Heudier, M., Mouillot, D. and L. Mannocci. 2023. Assessing the effects of coral reef habitat and marine protected areas on threatened megafauna using aerial surveys. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 33(3): 286-297.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3923>
- Hines, A.H., Whitlatch, R.B., Thrush, S.F., Hewitt, J.E., Cummings, V.J., Dayton, P., et al. 1997. Nonlinear foraging response of a large marine predator to benthic prey: eagle ray pits and bivalves in a New Zealand sandflat. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 216: 191–210. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981\(97\)00096-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981(97)00096-8)
- Hulberg, L.W. and J.S. Oliver. 1980. Caging manipulations in marine soft-bottom communities: importance of animal interactions or sedimentary habitat modifications. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 37(7): 1130-1139.
<https://doi.org/10.1139/f80-145>
- Johnson, C.R., Sutton, D.C., Olson, R.R. and R., Giddins. 1991. Settlement of crown-of-thorns starfish: role of bacteria on surfaces of coralline algae and a hypothesis for deepwater recruitment. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 71: 143-162. <https://www.int-res.com/articles/meps/71/m071p143.pdf>
- Kayal, M. 2024. Eagle ray feeding on a shallow coral reef in New Caledonia. Aerial video footage, 2 min 45 sec. <https://youtu.be/sxdbiZJmX1Y>
- Kayal, M., Vercelloni, J., Lison de Loma, T., Bosserelle, P., Chancerelle, Y., Geoffroy, S., et al. 2012. Predator crown-of-thorns starfish (*Acanthaster planci*) outbreak, mass mortality of corals, and cascading effects on reef fish and benthic communities. *PLOS ONE* e47363. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0047363>

- Kroon, F.J., Barneche, D.R. and M.J. Emslie. 2021. Fish predators control outbreaks of Crown-of-Thorns Starfish. *Nature Communications* 12(1): 6986.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26786-8>
- Lenihan, H.S. and F. Micheli. 2001. Soft sediment communities. Pages 253-287 in Bertness, M., Hay, M.E., and S.D. Gaines, editors. *Marine Community Ecology*. Sinauer Associates.
- Leray, M., Yang, J.Y., Meyer, C.P., Mills, S.C., Agudelo, N., Ranwez, V., et al. 2013. A new versatile primer set targeting a short fragment of the mitochondrial COI region for metabarcoding metazoan diversity: application for characterizing coral reef fish gut contents. *Frontiers in Zoology* 10: 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-9994-10-34>
- Matthews, S.A., Mellin, C. and M.S. Pratchett. 2020. Larval connectivity and water quality explain spatial distribution of crown-of-thorns starfish outbreaks across the Great Barrier Reef. *Advances in Marine Biology* 87(1): 223-258.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.amb.2020.08.007>
- McCauley, D.J., Pinsky, M.L., Palumbi, S.R., Estes, J.A., Joyce, F.H. and R.R. Warner. 2015. Marine defaunation: animal loss in the global ocean. *Science*, 347(6219): 1255641.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1255641>
- McCook, L.J., Ayling, T., Cappo, M., Choat, J.H., Evans, R.D., De Freitas, D.M., et al. 2010. Adaptive management of the Great Barrier Reef: a globally significant demonstration of the benefits of networks of marine reserves. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(43): 18278-18285. www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.0909335107
- Mellin, C., MacNeil, A.M., Cheal, A.J., Emslie, M.J. and J.M. Caley. 2016. Marine protected areas increase resilience among coral reef communities. *Ecology Letters*, 19(6): 629-637.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12598>

- Pimiento, C., Leprieur, F., Silvestro, D., Lefcheck, J.S., Albouy, C., Rasher, D.B., et al. 2020. Functional diversity of marine megafauna in the Anthropocene. *Science Advances* 6(16): eaay7650. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aay7650>
- Pratchett, M.S., Caballes, C.F., Rivera-Posada, J.A. and H.P. Sweatman. 2014. Limits to Understanding and Managing Outbreaks of Crown-of-Thorns Starfish (*Acanthaster* spp.). *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an annual review* 52: 133-244. CRC Press.
- Pratchett, M.S., Caballes, C.F., Wilmes, J.C., Matthews, S., Mellin, C., Sweatman, H.P., et al. 2017. Thirty years of research on crown-of-thorns starfish (1986–2016): scientific advances and emerging opportunities. *Diversity* 9(4): 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d9040041>
- Sweatman, H. 2008. No-take reserves protect coral reefs from predatory starfish. *Current Biology* 18(14): R598-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2008.05.033>
- Thistle, D. 1981. Natural physical disturbances and communities of marine soft bottoms. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 6(2): 223-228. <https://www.int-res.com/articles/meps/6/m006p223.pdf>
- Thrush, S.F., Pridmore, R.D., Hewitt, J.E. and V.J. Cummings. 1991. Impact of ray feeding disturbances on sandflat macrobenthos: do communities dominated by polychaetes or shellfish respond differently? *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 69: 245–252. <https://www.int-res.com/articles/meps/69/m069p245.pdf>
- VanBlaricom, G.R. 1982. Experimental analyses of structural regulation in a marine sand community exposed to oceanic swell. *Ecological Monographs* 52(3): 283-305. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2937332>

- Vanhatalo, J., Hosack, G.R. and H. Sweatman. 2017. Spatiotemporal modelling of crown-of-thorns starfish outbreaks on the Great Barrier Reef to inform control strategies. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 54(1): 188-197. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12710>
- Westcott, D.A., Fletcher, C.S., Kroon, F.J., Babcock, R.C., Plagányi, E.E., Pratchett, M.S. et al. 2020. Relative efficacy of three approaches to mitigate Crown-of-Thorns Starfish outbreaks on Australia's Great Barrier Reef. *Scientific Reports* 10(1): 12594. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-69466-1>
- Wilmes, J.C., Caballes, C.F., Cowan, Z.L., Hoey, A.S., Lang, B.J., Messmer, V. and M.S. Pratchett. 2018. Contributions of pre-versus post-settlement processes to fluctuating abundance of crown-of-thorns starfishes (*Acanthaster* spp.). *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 135: 332-345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2018.07.006>
- Wilmes, J.C., Hoey, A.S. and M.S. Pratchett, 2020a. Contrasting size and fate of juvenile crown-of-thorns starfish linked to ontogenetic diet shifts. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* 287(1931): 20201052. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2020.1052>
- Wilmes, J.C., Schultz, D.J., Hoey, A.S., Messmer, V. and M.S. Pratchett. 2020b. Habitat associations of settlement-stage crown-of-thorns starfish on Australia's Great Barrier Reef. *Coral Reefs* 39(4): 1163-1174. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-020-01950-6>
- Wooldridge, S.A. and J.E. Brodie. 2015. Environmental triggers for primary outbreaks of crown-of-thorns starfish on the Great Barrier Reef, Australia. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 101(2) : 805-815. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2015.08.049>
- Zann L., Brodie J., Berryman C. and M. Naqasima. 1987. Recruitment, ecology, growth and behavior of juvenile *Acanthaster planci* (L.)(Echinodermata: Asteroidea). *Bulletin of Marine Science* 41(2): 561-575.